

BIM

prove

D2.4 – Detailed Description of the Safety Functionalities and Worker Notifications – V2

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D2.4 Detailed description of the safety functionalities and worker notifications – V2

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Abstract

This deliverable covers safety functionalities focusing on two main topics. First, automatic detection of safety risk factors from photographs and point clouds and managing results is described. Secondly, an approach to locating and tracking assets as well as workers at construction sites is presented. The focus of the work done is in handling fall and fire risks. The deliverable also covers how to notify workers on safety risks.

Keywords

Safety, Risk, Object detection, Asset localization, Tracking, Notification

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTS	Asset Localization and Tracking System
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
H&S	Health & Safety
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
ML	Machine Learning
REST	Representational State Transfer
WNS	Worker Notification System

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. Introduction

Purpose of this document is to describe the BIMprove functionalities that are specific to support safety at the construction sites. The rate of work accidents in the construction domain is high. Safety risk for an individual worker depends on many risk factors including occupation type (e.g. a roofer vs a concrete worker), activity type (e.g. variation in used tools), temporal and spatial factors (e.g. work duration or concurrent activities), and used safety management controls (e.g. safety planning, training, and use of protection systems) (Choe & Leite 2020). Recently, there have been steps to digitalise health and safety (H&S) management. For example, there have been developed approaches for safety planning at design phase with integrating safety objects to BIM (Cortés-Pérez et al. 2020; Getuli et al. 2017), for automating H&S inspections (Kolar et al. 2018; Fang, Li, et al. 2018; Fang, Ding, et al. 2018), and hazard assessment (Amiri et al. 2017). There are also commercial tools for supporting H&S at construction sites. The aim of the functionalities described here is to mitigate safety risks by monitoring the safety status at a construction site and notifying workers of potential safety risks supplementing the previous and existing developments and functionalities. Especially, the focus here is in protecting workers from falling from heights and in detecting fire hazards.

The risk of falling can be mitigated by using fall protection systems. (OSHA 2015) classifies conventional fall protection systems into guardrail systems, safety nets, and personal fall arrest systems. Other fall protection systems include positioning devices that allow working with both hands free while on an elevated vertical surface and fall restraint systems that do not allow fall of any distance. Additional fall protection can be provided with warning lines on a roof to visually indicate unprotected and avoidable areas, using controlled access zones, and with safety monitoring systems that a designated person uses to monitor workers and to warn them when they are close to a fall hazard. According to BIMprove deliverable 1.8, the most frequent fire related scenarios include untidy construction sites, heat sources or electricity related not supervised, potentially dangerous tasks, managing negligence, untrained personnel, incorrect material warehousing, blocked emergency exits, and adjoining buildings or structures.

Relationships to other deliverables in BIMprove project:

- The functionalities are based on the requirements defined in D1.8 Risk and safety assessment methods
- External interfaces are defined in D1.5 Data Integration Interfaces for Building Industry using BIM and Digital Building Twins

The conceptual model of safety risk management is presented in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. Conceptual model

The conceptual model presents a high level view to safety risk functionalities. The safety risk management is divided into five modules. The intent of Computer Vision Model Creation is to train a model for visually detecting safety barriers, safety nets, and untidy places i.e. garbage from pictures taken at construction sites. A set of annotated images is required as training data for such model. The intent of the Risk Situation Detection module is to use the created model to analyse images taken at construction sites. In case a potential risk situation is found, then it is first clarified whether that is a new finding or is it already in the risk database. Potential new risks or changes in risk situation are also confirmed by H&S workers before adding them to the database. Risk Data Management module contains a risk database where the risk information is stored. Asset Localization and Tracking takes care of the locating various resources including workers. Finally, the intent of the Worker Notification module is to use the risk information and sensor data to alert workers of risk situations. While some of the modules in the conceptual model may be implemented with other BIMprove functionalities, at least short description of each module is given in the following chapters. However, the focus of this deliverable is in the computer vision model and the asset locating and tracking.

2. Computer Vision Model Creation

The automated detection of safety factors and risks is based on detecting from the visual material the conditions and situations which may contribute to formation of a risk. The digital visual material, photographs, videos or even laser scanned point clouds, collected from the work site may be analysed to detect the potential risks and related factors with a suitable deep learning based computer vision solution. Before reaching such capability, a deep neural networks model needs to be trained, as in any other data based machine learning solutions, using a suitable training data set. For the deep learning purposes with the selected model architecture, the training data needs to be gathered, stored, quality controlled and annotated with suitable labels.

2.1. Object Detection in 2D Images

The machine learning based computer vision model is trained for detecting risks or risk countermeasures at the construction sites. In general, this requires substantial amounts of training data in a form of digital images and/or video containing such features as wished to be detected. The quality of the images is important in two senses. Firstly, semantically they should contain what is desired to be detected and secondly technical quality should be reasonable regarding resolutions etc. The resolution usually may have an impact on the final detection precision but for training and detection they are always practically scaled down to a fixed size as dictated by the detection algorithm. However, if the final detection system should be robust and able to detect even in less than perfect conditions some, even manmade, imperfections are desired in the training data. The raw digital material as such is not enough to reach the adequate levels of detection precision in the final model within a reasonable computing time. Thus, the training data needs to be refined manually with an annotation process that should highlight those risk objects on the images as identified in the corresponding risk model. Especially in this case annotation classes will include safety barriers and safety nets as risk countermeasures; and piles of garbage as a fire risk factor with locating and labelling bounding boxes as in the Figure 2 and Figure 3 original and annotated image respectively. Sample images in this document are provided by the courtesy of HRS possessing all rights to the original images.

Figure 2. Original raw image from the construction site. (Copyright HRS)

Figure 3. Labelled and annotated image from the construction site. Annotation here contains barrier and garbage labels with bounding boxes and their x and y coordinates for illustrative purposes only. (Copyright HRS)

The annotation process produces training data capturing samples of the needed classes with a class label including the location of the item with a bounding box. The boxes' location on the original image's coordinate space consists of x, y coordinates of the upper left, and lower right corners for each labelled instance. The detection system when operational will be able to detect and predict these same attributes from the construction site images for further usage in risk analysis. The annotation and the output of detection system will, thus, contain the following:

Class – object class: barrier | net | garbage

x1 – upper left corner x-coordinate of the bounding box

y1 – upper left corner y-coordinate of the bounding box

x2 – lower right corner x-coordinate of the bounding box

y2 – lower right corner y-coordinate of the bounding box

Many of the freely available tools will be applicable for the annotation work and produce suitable annotations for the training data.

The iterative model creation process may include several training and verifying cycles. In each cycle we try to find suitable model architecture and its neural network training and hyperparameters to improve the overall detection precision. The current trend in the visual object detection and image classification is towards the deep convolutional neural networks. These outlay a challenge on the available data quantities and quality but also on the available computing resources. This usually means GPU resources very beneficial for parallel floating point operations evidential in ML processes. To maintain a reasonable time frame in the training process finetuning pre-existing models and transfer learning procedure should be favoured. The finetuning and transfer learning utilizes an existing model to diversify it to detect new classes of objects in the new domain. The results of the training cycles may also suggest deficiencies in the data and corrective requirements may be communicated to the training data gathering and creation processes that are, however, outside of this context. Should the training be successful, in the end the system should be able to produce detections following the same scheme as in the training data described earlier, which includes the object label and its approximate location on the provided image.

In the object detection application domain various models based on the convolutional networks have proved to be suitable and precise enough. Solutions like Faster R-CNN (Ren 2017) and various versions of Yolo (Redmon 2018) has evidentially been highly performing even with video feeds while maintaining adequate detection precision. Figure 4 represents ResNet-101 (He 2016) solution for object classification and localization architecture.

Figure 4. Convolutional network based ResNet with convolutional layers C1-C5 consisting of 64, 128, 256, 512 and 512 internal layers respectively completed with two fully connected (fc) layers of size 2048 neurons responsible for output of detected object classification and bounding box dimensions. Image source (Ding 2019).

As the current tendency is towards the even deeper and more complex machine learning model architectures, we cannot ignore the performance costs of such solutions. It may be desirable if the created model would maintain high level of precision in detection but also allow detection processing on the handheld devices with a live video streaming material also as many handheld devices possess substantial amounts of graphic displaying but also AI targeted GPU processing power. Initially, however, the detection is intended to be provided as a server based service contributing visual analysis results for the knowledge based final risk analysis processes as described later.

2.2. Object Detection in 3D point clouds

The mostly similar boundaries, conditions and processing phases apply also when working with the object detection in 3D point clouds as with the 2D images. However, the differences are mostly introduced along the additional dimension on the source data. This is evident in higher complexity of the deep learning models and data collection and preparation for the learning purposes. This directly means higher demand for the storage space and computing resources.

Here, as a training data source we will rely on the 3D point clouds and images captured by the flying drone and roving robot. The photogrammetrically fused LIDAR scans and photographs from the project's sample building in Madrid forms a full 3D illustration. Figure 5 illustrates outside corner of the sample building scans with the safety nets visible. This sample file alone contains over 23 million data points.

Figure 5. Provided photogrammetric data file combining stitched LIDAR scans and photographs illustrating a 3D view outside of the building. Data is provided by the courtesy of ZHAW and Robotnik.

The annotation process to label the objects of interest in such point clouds is a similar process as with the images in 2D case described earlier. The additional dimension, however, will make the amount of data higher and working with the labelling tools more challenging. In this case, the

photogrammetric nature and high density of the point clouds aids the recognizing the labelable objects for the human eyes. This is not necessarily the case with the regular sparse raw LIDAR scans. On the other hand, the density of the point cloud data and thus vast data size burdens the processing of them for object detection purposes. One possible solution is to slice and crop data to a more processable pieces.

Some ready labelled data sets exist e.g., several for autonomous driving but also for the construction industry. Some benchmarking data sets for detection of the constructed building structures itself exist like IFC datasets (Emunds et al 2021). Such typically lack the object classes required here, namely the safety nets and barriers. To create a more robust and reliable detection model, a fully or at least partially automated process would be desirable in data set labelling. Such could be achievable with the aid of the 2D image object detection solution sketched in the earlier section. Another option would be the utilization of detection model architectures like MVX-NET (Sindagi, et. al. 2019) capable of utilizing multi-modal input data consisting of the point clouds and location images. However, their benefits are questioned e.g. in (Zhang, et. al. 2020), which also sees augmentation procedures as better options.

Two main types, namely image-based and various forms of point-cloud-based detection, methods exist. (Duarte, et. al. 2021). First of the 3D point cloud object detection solutions use 2D projected bitmap images from the point cloud views as detection basis. Other solutions utilize the points and their features or other volumetric presentations, e.g. voxels, instead extracting the detectable features from the point clouds. The 2D bitmap projection usually leads to a lower accuracy but consumes less computing resources, which are the opposite case for the feature extracting methods.

One very potential object detection model architecture is PointPillars (Lang, e.t. al, 2018). It is a deep learning architecture for object detection in the LIDAR produced point cloud streams. It employs a somewhat similar approach as YOLO for the 2D image based operations. These approaches include initial Single Shot Detection, SSD, style anchor box creation and other input data pre-processing techniques intended for a fast inference for the real time processing needs. Typical distinction between the various point cloud object detection approaches is the utilized voxelization method. The voxelization is a discretization process of producing a reduced size representation of the original point cloud data. This intermediate representation, even though removing data and features, should still capture enough features to allow precise enough object detection on the succeeding layers of the neural network model. This intermediate form is presented as a pseudo image to the 2D convolutional network based object detection algorithms, like in many other image based detection models. The Figure 6 (Lang, e.t. al, 2018) below outlines the PointPillars model architecture for the object detection in point clouds.

Figure 6.. PointPillars object detection deep learning model architecture for point clouds. (Lang, e.t. al, 2018)

3. Risk Situation Detection

The purpose of risk situation detection is to support the work of H&S personnel in detecting either new risk situations or updating the status of an earlier found risk. BIMprove project focuses on detecting safety barriers, safety nets, and untidy places in images taken at the construction site. The images are taken by robots, drones, or construction workers at the construction site. The location of the scene the image has been taken of should be mapped to the BIMprove coordinate system. The actual process for this will be defined when integrating BIMprove functionalities.

The visual potential safety factor and risk detection is done by using the available image or video data from the construction site. The visual material is assessed with the computer vision solution for which a deep learning based model was created earlier. The arriving digital material submitted for the analysis needs a storage solution before the visual risk detection will take place. The results and the potential findings from the visual material are subsequently submitted to the risk database for further integration and analysis with the existing knowledge. The results data may include among other data also the analysed image with the detected and highlighted risk objects for human verification and viewing.

4. Risk Data Management

Note: Risk data management presented in this chapter describes the test environment used for computer vision model. The actual risk data management used in BIMprove project will be implemented via BIMSyc and BCF issues.

Risk data management described here includes i) using a common vocabulary and taxonomy for defining the main concepts and relationships between concepts, ii) storing risk related data into a graph database, the database is structured based on the defined risk taxonomy and iii) assessing

discovered risks and notifying workers on possible threats. In this chapter, the required elements for the comprehensive risk management approach are described in more detail.

4.1. Risk ontology

A current trend in the construction industry is that the work is more often done by multidisciplinary and geographically dispersed teams. However, members of distributed teams may have difficulty establishing a shared context (Pallot 2011). The absence of shared context impedes the reaching of mutual understanding, which may significantly impact collaboration effectiveness and efficiency (Pallot et al. 2010; Clark and Brennan, 1991). An increasingly utilized method to facilitate common understanding between members of a collaborative team is the use ontologies. By definition, ontology is an explicit and formal specification of a conceptualisation of a domain of interest (Gruber 1993). Furthermore, ontology is defined as a controlled vocabulary that describes objects and the relations between them in a formal way (Berners-Lee et al. 2001). Finally, ontologies, provide effective machine-to-machine communication capabilities enabling computational entities and services to have a common set of concepts and vocabularies for representing knowledge about a domain of interest (Wang et al. 2002).

In BIMProve, all data related to safety risks is modelled with a specific risk data management ontology. The ontology aims at formally representing risk-specific concepts and their relationships, and metadata that enables the system to better understand and reason about the structure and purpose of the data. Moreover, it constitutes a common data representation for the heterogeneous group of stakeholders participating in the safety risk management on the construction site. The current version of the risk ontology is represented in the Figure 7. As can be seen, some class definitions of the ontology are still incomplete. Hence, for example the class “RiskZone” contains no properties at this stage.

Figure 7. First version of the risk ontology

The first version of the risk ontology is defined based on the concepts and terms that are identified in BIMProve as essential for risk management. The central class in the ontology is Risk that has certain data properties such as name and description. In addition, the Risk class is associated with a risk level that is divided into several subclasses representing different risk levels. The class Risk can also be linked with different risk types (i.e. fire and fall from heights) and risk zones. In addition, instances of the class Risk can also have images that represent characteristics of a risk.

The objective of the class Image is to capture the knowledge extracted from pictures taken from a construction site. It holds two data properties that are URL (pointing to the storage location of the image) and ID of the image. The Image class is associated with the RiskRelatedObject class that models the concepts that are essential for the above described “Automated Detection of Safety Factors and Risks” service. In more detail, the class defines the information that can be automatically detected from the pictures by the utilized deep learning-based computer vision solution. The RiskRelatedObject class has three subclasses that are SafetyNet, Garbage and Barrier. These subclasses represents concrete physical objects that are automatically detected from images. The xMin, xMax, yMin and yMax data properties (See Figure 3) capture the anchor box where a detected object is located in an image. Furthermore, the data property hasConfidence represents a confidence score that is the probability that a defined anchor box contains the detected object.

4.2. Use of risk database

As described in the previous chapter, the data model defined for describing safety risks is highly connected. In other words, there exists multiple relationships between identified concepts, which sets specific requirements for a selected database technology to store this kind of data. During the recent years, the limitations of traditional databases, in particular the relational model, to cover the requirements of current application domains, has led the development of new technologies (Angles, 2012). In particular graph databases have increased in popularity. A graph database is a database designed to treat the relationships between data as equally important to the data itself (Kumar, 2019). The main benefits of graph databases include

- Performance - Improved performance by several orders of magnitude compared to traditional database (Dominguez-Sal et al. 2010)
- Flexibility – Can hold data without constricting it to a pre-defined model. The structure of the graph can evolve over time as needs and requirements clarify (Vicknair et al. 2010)

In the computer vision test environment, different safety risk related data is stored using the Apache Fuseki (Yang et al. 2018). Fuseki is a graph database server that enables storing data in an RDF (Resource Description Framework) format and querying it using the SPARQL query language. The data stored in the Fuseki database is structured according to the ontology described in the previous chapter. RDF and SPARQL are powerful, yet complex, ways to store and retrieve data. To flatten the required learning curve, a specifically designed API solution is developed in BIMprove to simplify the storing and acquiring of risk data. A high level architecture of the overall database solution is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. BIMProve database solution for storing and querying risk data

As shown in Figure 8, the simplified API to utilize Fuseki database service contains two access methods. The REST (Representational State Transfer) based API enables other systems and software to programmatically update and query the database. For example, the Automated detection of safety factors and risks module described earlier utilizes this method to access the risk database. The HTML based web user interface enables human users to manage the database contents. It allows, for example, to add new database instances through a simple web page form. Additionally, it enables retrieving data contained by the database either in textual or visual form.

The above mentioned REST API accepts JSON data as input parameters. Figure 9 represents an example JSON structure that defines a risk related object that was identified from an image by the Automated detection of safety factors and risks module. As can be seen, the input parameters follow the properties of the data model described in the previous chapter. The input parameters contain, for example, the ID and URL of the image that was analysed, type of the risk related object and coordinates of the anchor box that specifies the part of the picture the object is located in.

```

11 lines (11 sloc) 255 Bytes
1 {
2   "imageID": "z9MHIIjZQ0",
3   "name": "safetynet",
4   "confidence": "0.485",
5   "xmax": "925.186",
6   "xmin": "481.6767",
7   "ymax": "964.23455",
8   "ymin": "712.9662",
9   "imageURL": "https://bit.ly/3glwtiH",
10  "anchorBoxImageURL": "https://bit.ly/3glwtiH"
11 }
    
```

Figure 9. Example input data defining a risk related object extracted from an image

An example of the web page UI to access Fuseki database is shown in Figure 10. In this view, results of the image analysis module are represented in a table format. The table lists images and risk related objects identified from the images. The table is sorted based on the image IDs.

Image ID	Risk related object	Confidence	xmax	xmin	ymax	ymin	Image URL	Image URL with anchor box
79bdJnMipL	safetynet	0.357	325.767	148.123	431.346	239.687	Image	Image with anchor box
f52-oi0NhG	garbage	0.567	986.545	477.566	789.57	567.766	Image	Image with anchor box
K9MHIIjZQ0	barrier	0.289	925.186	481.677	964.235	712.966	Image	Image with anchor box
tsoyrxA6S8	barrier	0.234	789.443	345.866	876.312	436.529	Image	Image with anchor box
tsoyrxA6S8	garbage	0.567	234.447	100.566	343.344	97.454	Image	Image with anchor box
z9MHIIjZQ0	safetynet	0.485	925.186	481.677	964.235	712.966	Image	Image with anchor box

Figure 10. Screenshot from the Fuseki database web UI

In the following phases of the project, both access methods to the database will be extended and updated to address various requirements of the safety functionalities and worker notifications developed in BIMprove.

4.3. Integration with the Bimsync tool

In order to increase the visibility and accessibility of the results of the object detection module, an integration between the image analysis engine and the Bimsync platform was established. This means that whenever safety risk factors are detected from photographs, the results are subsequently submitted to the Bimsync. The integration is implemented utilizing the Bimsync REST API v2, which supports, e.g., the exchange of BCF issues between software applications via a RESTful web interface. In addition, a dedicated Python application (i.e. BimsyncProxy) was developed to transform the output of the object detection module into the format specified by the Bimsync REST API v2.

The results of the object detection are inserted to Bimsync as new issues. The developed integration approach is represented in Figure 11. As can be seen, the results of the object detection module are submitted to the BimsyncProxy as a JSON string. The BimsyncProxy then transforms the data into the format understood by the Bimsync. As a result, a new issue is created in Bimsync that contains the object detection result data.

Figure 11. Integration of the object detection engine and the Bimsync tool

The Figure 12 shows, how the results of the object detection module appear in the Bimsync graphical user interface. As represented in the image, the original file name of the analysed image is used as a baseline when generating unique IDs for new Bimsync issues. In addition, the description section of the issue contains the results of the object detection in a human-readable format. In this case, a barrier was detected from the analysed image with the confidence score of 0.2570853531. Next both of the images (original and the one with yellow bounding boxes) are shown in the issue view. Finally,

raw object detection data in JSON format is represented in the comment section. The raw JSON data is also constructed using the concepts and terms defined in the risk ontology described in Chapter 4.1.

Figure 12. Results of the object detection module in Bimsync graphical user interface

The above described integration effort facilitates the linking of the object detection approach with other functionalities developed and utilized over the course of the BIMprove project. With Bimsync, various stakeholders involved in construction site operations can access the results of the automatic safety risk factor detection in a visual, concise and easily understandable way.

5. Asset Localization and Tracking

Locating and tracking of essential equipment and materials that are only available in low quantity or volume, can be very important in construction site planning and scheduling. However, we focus here more on the topic of worker localization and tracking which is essential for giving sensible worker safety notifications.

Figure 13. Entity relationship-like diagram illustrating the proposed basic architecture for an ALTS as implemented with mixed BluEpyc and standard BLE-capable PC Bluetooth radio devices. Hardware entities are shown as boxes while software entities are shown as ellipses.

5.1. Devices and Basic Architecture

The hardware we are currently pursuing a solution with is based on devices from the company BluEpyc (<https://www.bluepyc.com>), a business unit under SOFTWORK Group (<https://www.softwork.it/>). But also ordinary BLE-capable radios on PCs, such as the one in a Raspberry Pi 3 or 4, can be used and participate in tag tracking; in the following dubbed *tagging*. This section goes through the major entities in the proposed basic architecture.

Figure 13 shows an example object diagram of a minimal system of mixed BluEpyc and ordinary PC BLE-radio devices as primary BLE receivers and the software stacks involved up to the level of tag trackers (*Traggers*) and logging database.

5.1.1. Hardware Devices

BLE Tag Beacons, or simply **Tags**, are small, mobile, battery powered beacons that are carried by workers or attached to equipment. These may have several facilities depending of type and make. Different tag devices are able to provide information from sensors, such as battery level, acceleration, temperature, humidity, button interaction etc. Some tag devices are also able to take input commands for making visual, vibratory, or auditory alarms. Many such features may be

essential in improving a worker notification system (WNS), but the central feature to tracking in our context is simply the ability to determine that a mobile tag beacon is within range of a stationary beacon and with what signal strength.

Devices with BLE radios are used as stationary beacons for localizing tags into their zones. In our proposed system we plan on using only EchoBeacons from BluEpyc as the direct BLE receiver. The implemented software is also able to use the BluEpyc gateways as a direct tag receiver, and even standard BLE radios in PCs, laptops, or Raspberry Pis may be used for direct tag receivers.

BluEpyc EchoBeacons, or simply *EchoBeacons*, are devices with a BLE radio, acting as the primary receivers which make the direct BLE interaction with the tags. EchoBeacons have a configurable behaviour and associate with BluEpyc Gateways for both data exchange in operation but also for configuration.

BluEpyc Gateways, or simply *Gateways*, are devices with a BLE radio and an Ethernet port for integrating the geometrically dispersed EchoBeacons into the overall information system. A Gateway acts mainly as a secondary receiver with respect to tags, collecting the tag data streams from several EchoBeacons. However, a Gateway can also, in itself, act as a primary receiver, just like an EchoBeacon. Configuration of the Gateways, and the EchoBeacons via the Gateways, can currently only be performed from a proprietary BluEpyc software called "Start". The protocol is described for the API over Ethernet/TCP to the Gateways, such that configuration and interaction can be realized programmatically in the system during operation. However, we have not developed such software yet, and we distinguish sharply between state of operation and state of configuration on a per-Gateway granularity.

5.1.2. Software Entities

A **BluEpycReader** object has a connection to a specific BluEpyc Gateway in an operational state. When in an operational state, the Gateway streams observations of tags, directly observed and observed via associated EchoBeacons, to a configured Ethernet/TCP endpoint. A particular Gateway must thus be configured to match a particular BluEpycReader. The set of BluEpycReaders is the lower level medium for the tag data stream into the overall ALTS. The function of the BluEpycReader is to isolate the tag-related information from the stream of much other information from the associated Gateway.

A **BluePyReader** object is a reader that directly reads a BLE radio on a PC with the software library `bluepy` as a primary receiver, hence the name. The function and data provided upward in the ALTS is identical to that of the BluEpycReader. The BluePyReader is useful for experimentation since no BluEpyc devices are necessary for setting up and testing an ALTS.

A **MulticastAdapter** object is a specific adapter that can convey the BluEpycReader information via an IP multicast stream. Multicasting is a technique where data packets are distributed efficiently to all members of a multicast group.

A **Receiver** object is a member of a multicast group for receiving the stream of multicast packets from a Reader and selects out the relevant packages from the primary BLE receiver it is configured to represent. In Figure 13 any Receiver is associated by a dotted curve to exactly one primary BLE receiver; i.e. to a BluEpyc EchoBeacon, a BluEpyc Gateway, or a BLE Radio. A Receiver will maintain and keep a short history of the population of tags and their observed signal strengths.

A **Tragger** object localizes and tracks the specific tag it is configured for. A Tragger must scout for, and establish connection to the Receivers which have current or recent observations on the tag which the Tragger tracks. The function of the Tragger is to determine at any time with which, if any, primary BLE receiver, and hence zone, its configured tag is located.

The **Logger** object is shown in Figure 13 only to illustrate that there may be some aspect in the architecture which represents long term data storage for various purposes; such as on-site or off-site analysis, traceability of the building process, or dissemination into other business systems.

5.2. Reliability, Stability, and Responsiveness in Traggering

If the primary receivers, i.e. the EchoBeacons, are strongly geometrically dispersed, meaning that their maximum coverage zones are non-overlapping, we have full temporal separation among observations of the tags and there is no challenge for a Tragger. In such case it should simply report the latest zone of observation of its tag, and possibly report "no location" if the time since last observation is too long. A setup with good coverage, however, will have overlapping coverage zones for the primary receivers, and there will be challenges with reliably, stably, and accurately localizing a tag to one particular zone at any time.

An essential part of developing the ALTS is that logic in the Traggers has to be designed for the correct compromise between stability, responsiveness, and reliability. *Stability* addresses to what degree a Tragger will have a definitive response to queries such as where its tag currently is, where it have been and where it is probably currently heading. *Reliability* addresses the extend to which such responses from a Tragger can be considered true or trustworthy. *Responsiveness* addresses how quickly such responses can be replied.

As is often the case in real-time cyber-physical systems, which involves sensor systems and computation for inferring model or unobservable states in real-time, the trade-off among the aforementioned trinity is very important. E.g. any system can be brought to be highly stable and responsive by simply responding with a fixed value or reply, which then deems the system highly

unreliable. A system based on very sophisticated physical models with a lot of heuristic computation involved may be classified as unstable, unreliable, and unresponsive altogether, even though correct results will come out once in a while, even quickly; some things are simply hard to model or compute.

Different uses of ALTS may have different requirements to this trade-off. An equipment localization system will probably emphasize the correctness of the reply, i.e. reliability, and be more relaxed towards stability or responsiveness. Work progress tracking will probably be of a more statistical nature, will not pose any real-time requirements, and will thus only emphasize that some data are more or less stably recorded and stored, and that the data are more or less trustworthy, but not at all how quickly the data was acquired and stored at the time of observation.

We plan to initially implement a simple, calibration-free, tuneable computing model for tag localization to zones based on latest and recent observations of signal strengths in primary receivers across the system. One parameter may determine the weight between the latest and the recent observations, and another parameter may determine how much of the past observations are taken as recent. Such a model will determine *de facto* zones, determined by the discrimination in the system, and with some dynamic zone boundaries depending on the recent observations of the individual tags. These *de facto* zones will not strictly follow the designed zones, but the amount of discrepancy will be unknown until tested.

Figure 14. Floor plan example with distribution of Tags, EchoBeacons, Gateways and Raspberry Pis. Gateways are connected to their controller Raspberry Pis by wired Ethernet connection (solid red); EchoBeacons are connected to their controlling Gateway by BLE (dashed blue); Raspberry Pis are interconnected in a Wi-Fi mesh network (dashed red); and Tags are connected to the EchoBeacons in range by temporary BLE connections (dotted blue). The signal coverage of the EchoBeacons are shown as radial gradients of green.

Figure 14 illustrates a section of a building floor plan with fixed devices and the connections among the devices. The identities of Gateways, EchoBeacons, and Raspberry Pis must be linked to the

building geometry, possibly in the BIM model, i.e. the relevant system components running on the Raspberry Pis have to be configured to know the node location, the identity and location of the connected Gateway, and the identities and locations of the EchoBeacons to service.

One particular point in Figure 14 is that the relation of zones, rooms, and EchoBeacon coverage must be clarified. Currently, in the initial prototype, we do not consider rooms in the system, but associate zones with EchoBeacon in a one to one manner, where zone boundaries are determined by strength of signal. The geometrical placement of EchoBeacons in the building and tags on workers and equipment may be very important in getting a good correlation between measured signal strength and position.

An immediate, but probably operationally expensive, improvement is to do a calibration by moving a tag around the entire site, at least tracing all design zone boundaries, according to a known trajectory. This will give an authoritative hint for correlating signal strengths to zone association. However, there will always be dynamic uncertainty at the precise zone boundaries, irregardless of whether we consider designed or *de facto* boundaries. The cost mentioned is the cost of performing the calibration underlay by moving a tag in a controlled way around the site. If this is to be a manual operation, it will be expensive in operator time. However, if UGVs that patrol the whole site can be used in this respect, the calibration will be a continuous process in ALTS and, in principle, it will not be associated with any extra operational costs.

5.3. Distributed Computing Architecture

The simple fact that at the very lowest level we have independent, physically separated devices that performs computing routines and communicate wirelessly makes the overall system a distributed computing system in principle. However, if all Ethernet connections to the Gateways were routed via a simple switched network to a single PC with one process running the higher level ALTS operations, this should rather be classified as a centralized or monolithic computing system.

Even if it would be possible and feasible to make such a centralized ALTS, it will, from both computing, scalability, and resilience points of view, be more interesting to make the system as strongly distributed as possible. We take inspiration and draw on experience from the topics cyber-physical systems and multi-agent systems.

The Raspberry Pis are the computational nodes over which an ALTS, and, later on, a WNS, is deployed. They will host all the software entities shown in Figure 13 and described in the section "Software Entities". The set of Raspberry Pis covering a connected construction site must be on the same Ethernet. By connected we mean the geographic region over which mobile and movable assets are to be tracked. This could be the entire construction site covered by one ALTS, or it could be that each building block in a construction site could be covered by its own ALTS. In any case, the

nodes of one ALTS must be connected over Ethernet, and depending on existing infrastructure this may be via wired if wiring is existing or practical; managed wireless using existing or dedicated access points; or wireless IEEE 802.11s or *ad hoc* mesh network. The latter one may prove to be the most scalable and manageable general solution, unless throughput will be an issue. In the prototype we aim for setting up a small LAN network by either a wired or a Wi-Fi access point-based solution, whatever will be practical.

In the diagram in Figure 13 software objects are communicated and connected by standard Ethernet protocols; TCP/IP and Multicast. However, the communication type "Pyro" deserves some introduction. Pyro is

" [...] a library that enables you to build applications in which objects can talk to each other over the network, with minimal programming effort. You can just use normal Python method calls to call objects on other machines. Pyro is a pure Python library and runs on many different platforms and Python versions."

-- Irmen de Jong (<https://pyro4.readthedocs.io>)

The code base being developed uses Python as language. For communication and connection among Python objects distributed over various nodes, Pyro is a very easy and flexible solution. In short, a Python object deployed on one node can establish a proxy for directly invoking methods on a Python object deployed on another node, provided that the nodes are on the same Ethernet LAN.

Figure 15. Deployment diagram of an example system with two Raspberry Pis, two Gateways, four EchoBeacons, and five tags. Full lines symbolize direct connection while dashed lines symbolize configured associations. For clarity the MulticastAdapter objects have been squashed with the Reader objects, since they are one to one.

Deployment of software objects on the Raspberry Pis are illustrated in the deployment diagram in Figure 15. Essentially it reflects the same structure as the entity-relation-like diagram in Figure 13, but it is almost a genuine UML deployment diagram, emphasizing the structure into computational and device node. The diagram is simplistic since it omits the execution environments in the Raspberry Pi nodes, where each of the objects may be running in each their own Python process instance; the Reader and Receiver objects may be executing in one Python process with the Tragger objects in another Python process; or in one common Python process. This has to be determined by a balance of computational requirement in each object and practical concerns about management of a multitude of Python processes.

5.4. A Note on Protection of Worker Privacy

Worker localization and tracking is from a privacy and private data perspective a highly sensitive topic, which must be treated and insured properly in the pertinent subsystems.

There may be various sensor systems in play for worker localization and tracking, some of which may directly identify individuals by biometric data; e.g. computer vision-based localization systems may record and store enough data, such as images, to directly identify an individual worker, either by computer vision-based, but most certainly by human vision-based, facial recognition.

A good first step is anonymity of workers and randomization of temporary identifiers in the tracking system. Anonymity, in contrast to pseudonymity, means that nowhere in any part of the entire system there exists, or can be established, a mapping of worker identity to temporary system identifier. Randomization of identifiers means that there will be random variations in the identifiers associated with individual workers.

Depending on data recorded in the system as a whole, these steps may not be enough to ensure worker anonymity. Data records, such as motion patterns, known location pin-points, behaviours, etc., may be analysed together with other metadata to establish the correspondence between worker identity and temporary system identifiers over time. Ensuring against such correspondence is extremely hard.

6. Worker Notifications

A sensible worker notification system needs a set of known risks and their locations on a construction site, a tracking system for workers on the site, a medium of notification, and, possibly, a medium for acknowledgements from the notified workers.

Two important aspects, which can not be cleanly separated, are the medium for notifications and the logic of notifications.

6.1. Media

The medium of conveying notifications, as well as receiving back acknowledgements, may be more or less sophisticated, and it may be stationed on the location, or it may be an individual wearable device.

Notifications may be simple visual, auditory, or vibratory signals to the worker. Acknowledgement from the worker could be a simple push on a button on a wearable device.

A sophisticated candidate medium is any modern mobile phone, which allows all kinds of signals; video stream, visual, vibratory, audio stream, and auditory. And allows all kinds of feedback from the worker. An even more interesting feature of a device such as the mobile phone is that it supports several ways of communication, e.g. Wi-Fi may be used to control the notification to and acknowledgement from the worker, which may be much easier and more flexible than BLE communication. The BLE radio in the phone is thus solely used for localization and tracking.

The tags from BluEpyc, which we currently use, can emit light signals, via a red and a blue LED, and a button that can be used for acknowledgement. The procedure of interacting with the tags is somewhat elaborate, e.g. for issuing a notification and receiving an acknowledgement, and require a fair amount of involvement in BLE and the tag protocol and using GATT sessions, which is supported by the `bluepy`-library. This is ongoing work.

Figure 16. Sequence diagram for issuing a temporary worker notification.

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Figure 17. Sequence diagram for issuing an acknowledged worker notification.

The sequence diagrams in Figures 16 and 17 details the scenarios we see for us in our current understanding of BLE and tag interaction, for issuing temporary notifications and issuing notifications that require an acknowledgement. These are the two primitives that we currently imagine the WNS will be based on in the future.

The interactions initiated from a Tragger object with the tag is thought to be through the hosting Raspberry Pi’s BLE radio, and not via the BluEpyc system. The BluEpyc system is thus only part of the continuous ALTS aspect of localization and tracking. When interacting with a Tag, the Tragger must create a GATTSession object which performs some operations on the Tag. Temporary notifications are quite simple, as seen in Figure 16. Acknowledged notifications, shown in Figure 17, in addition require involvement from both the user and a relevant Receiver object. Between the start of notification, and before ending the notification, the Tragger object has to listen for advertisements, which are now proactively emitted from the Tag, and wait for an advertisement:Tag which states that the button has been pushed by the worker.

The interactions illustrated in Figures 16 and 17 indicate that the architecture and design for a WNS is not just a minor extension of the ALTS. This strongly affects design and deployment, and also coverage by extra BLE radios for WNS-interactions. In short, the Raspberry Pis shown associated with the Gateways in Figure 14 must be sufficiently densely represented to cover the entire target area with their BLE radios. The ones shown for the purpose of ALTS is only designed to secure coverage of the installed EchoBeacons via the Gateways. As WNS can not simply piggy-back on ALTS, a more elaborate architecture and design has to be developed for WNS.

One important challenge which the mechanistic design of WNS has to take into account is the temporal extent of the interactions between Tragger and Tag shown in Figures 16 and 17. There is no guarantee that the worker with the target tag does not move out of range of the stationary BLE radio of the pertinent Raspberry Pi used for the initiation of the notification interaction. Such disconnect or out of range events must be detected by the Tragger, a new BLE radio with the target Tag in range found, and the interaction resumed from where it was disrupted.

6.1.1. Wearable Device Placement Challenge

An important aspect of the localization and tracking system is the placement of the wearable on the worker. For isotropic signal strength, the BLE-device should be mounted on the helmet of the worker, where it is equally exposed to all EchoBeacons in range. However this poses a challenge with accessibility for the worker, notably for observing a visible notification. This suggests a requirement on the notification device to be able to give auditory or vibratory signals, since visible signals will not be observable by the worker, when the device is worn on the helmet.

A different approach may be taken, utilizing two tags on each worker. One tag for localization and tracking, worn on top of the helmet, and another tag mounted visibly on the wrist of the worker. This is entirely possible, but adds to the system complexity, since now a worker must register two tags when entering the site, and the system must keep these two tags associated information-wise. However, with the current hardware available, this seems the viable solution.

6.2. Logic

The logic of notifications deals with a mapping from risk type and level, and possibly individual worker preference, to the nature of notification interaction to undertake, taking the individual worker notification history into account. This section lists some of the types of notifications we can imagine to be sensible to provide.

The main elements in determining the act of issuing a notification are the event of a worker entering a risk zone and the state of a worker being in a risk zone. Notification issuance logic could be classified into

- **one-time:** Only on first entry, and never again or only on re-entry after a longer period.
- **episodic:** On every entry into the zone.
- **periodic:** Periodically with a given cycle time while the worker is in the zone.
- **continuous:** Constant warning while in the zone.

This classification of issuance logic must be coupled semantically with a more elaborate and detailed classification of notification types, such as those described by Figures 16 and 17. For instance, continuous notification is similar to, but not adequately described by the temporary notification type in Figure 16.

A continuous notification requires triggering by the event of worker entry into the zone, which turns on the notification signal on the worker wearable, which is left on for the duration of stay in the zone. Exit from the zone must then trigger the turning off of the notification signal. In addition, continuous notification is natural to associate with the highest levels of risk, and the scenario of notification may start with requiring an (episodic) acknowledged notification on entry into the zone, and perhaps even periodic acknowledged notifications while in the zone.

This mixing of temporary and acknowledge notifications makes it clear that we may need two different signals for notification, one for temporary or continuous notification and one for notifications requiring acknowledgement from the worker. Such distinct signals can be achieved if the Tag hardware allows for it, e.g. different auditory tones and volumes, different vibratory pitch and intensity, or different LED flash frequency and colour.

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